

We are glad to welcome you to SCENARIOS' first newsletter!

SCENARIOS is a 4-year H2020 Research and Innovation project (RIA) involving 19 partners from 10 European countries and Israel. The goal is to close the knowledge gap and achieve breakthrough TRL advances in the toxicology, detection and remediation of probably the most objectionable and widespread class of contaminants -PFAS-, with an unprecedented energetic balance and virtually no external chemical additives. A major effort is underway to develop Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment (IATA) of PFAS, including the new generation of congeners, to assist EC and EU countries in decision-making on these substances for environmental safety and human health.

SCENARIOS looks back at its achievements in the first year

During the first year of the project we have advance in the three research pilots of Scenarios:

- Smart detection of PFAS, we established gold standard analytical methods that will be used to generate data and validate two novel determination methods based on either Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering (SERS) and/or electrochemical microsensors. WE also got amazing results showing that it is possible to develop innovative approaches to accelerate the detection and identification of PFAS in environmental samples and human fluids
- The working group defined a panel of 34 congeners that considers a number of PFAS precursors such as PFOA, PFOS, and other substances with a carbon number greater than 8 atoms. The latter substances are referred to as PFASs with limited data because their effects on human populations and the environment are almost completely unknown. The scenario partners have studied the effects of these substances on different human cell systems (liver, lung, blood), highlighting the relative toxicity of these substances, activation of cell receptors such as PPAR-alpha, cytokine response, etc. These data were modelled and PFAS toxicity was classified according to different criteria in order to decipher the physicochemical, chemical or biochemical determinants that serve as drivers of toxicity.
- Quasi zero-energy PFAS remediation. Scenarios has confirmed and secured outstanding pilot sites to validate and demonstrate the new Scenarios technologies. We must mention the work done by the Scenarios partner Department of Integrated Activities Research and Innovation within the Alexandria Civil Hospital (UOAL), which made available its expertise in epidemiology to carry out the first PFAS biomonitoring in the human population in the districts of Alessandria (Italy) bordering a hot spot of PFAS emission. In addition, samples from the biobank have been selected to study the interference of PFAS against the Covid-19 vaccine.

NEWS

SCENARIOS 1st Year Summary

On December 12-13, 2022, we met again in Alessandria, Italy at the Department of Science and Technological Innovation of the University of Piemonte, this time in presence, to discuss the results of the first year of activity of the H2020-Scenarios project.

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SCENARIOS Kick-off meeting

On Thursday, 09th and Friday 10th December 2021 the Scenarios consortium held its kick-off meeting in a hybrid format in Alessandria, Italy where Prof. Francesco Dondero, Project Coordinator, acted as host from Università degli Studi del Piemonte Orientale.

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Kick off meeting for Green Deal Chemical Cluster

Today SCENARIOS was presented at the kick off meeting from the Green Deal Chemicals Cluster that lasted all morning. The presentation of SCENARIOS was made by our project coordinator Francesco Dondero. Sister projects were also presented there too, and a very interesting morning there were many very lively discussions on the issues, PFAS and legislation were especially hot topics.

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The H2020 SCENARIOS project is 100 percent in place

In July 2022 and most recently from September 11-15, six different teams from the SCENARIOS consortium met at the Trelleborg demonstration site in southern Sweden and the Korsor demonstration site in Zelandia, Denmark, to carry out important work related to research and demonstration tasks under this project funded by the H2020 program.

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SCENARIOS Seminar Series

As part of the annual meeting of the H2020-project SCENARIOS, the "First International Workshop on PFAS Transport and PFAS Toxicology" will feature high-level speakers and experts PFAS is the acronym for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances and represents a group of emerging contaminants known for their persistence and mobility in the environment.

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SCENARIOS 1st General Assembly

On Monday and Tuesday last week SCENARIOS held its first general assembly in Alessandria organised by the project coordinator Prof. Francesco Dondero and his team from the Department of Science and Technological Innovation, in the Università del Piemonte Orientale (UPO).

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Follow up on the "First International Workshop on PFAS transport and PFAS toxicology"

The "First International Workshop on PFAS transport and PFAS toxicology" was held last Monday December 12 on the Università del Piemonte Orientale premises in Alessandria organised by project coordinator Francesco Dondero and his team from the Department of Science and Technological Innovation.

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PUBLICATIONS & RESULTS

Six scientific papers have been already published in relation to the project:

- **Mechanisms of Individual and Simultaneous Adsorption of Antibiotics and Dyes onto Halloysite Nanoclay and Regeneration of Saturated Adsorbent via Cold Plasma Bubbling** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Bioconversion of hazardous organic wastes using invertebrates** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **A novel, green, low-cost regeneration method for surface enhanced raman scattering (SERS) solid substrates based on nanosecond pulsed cold plasma technology** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Key-study on plasma-induced degradation of cephalosporins in water: Process optimization, assessment of degradation mechanisms and residual toxicity** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **Bioconversion of polystyrene and food waste streams into biochar: an upgraded enzymatic activation system** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)
- **A Review on Removal and Destruction of Per- and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS) by Novel Membranes** [▶ LEARN MORE](#)

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